

Neurotic stress: US state resident neuroticism and state COVID-19 death rates

Stewart J. H. McCann
Cape Breton University (Canada)

Stewart_McCann@cbu.ca

Copyright. 2017–2024. Psychreg Journal of Psychology
An open access initiative by Psychreg Ltd
ISSN: 2515-138X

The purpose was to determine the potential of state resident Neuroticism to predict state COVID-19 death rates with state socioeconomic status, White population percent, urban population percent, percent of at-risk adults, percent of population 65 and over, percent of older adults with at least four chronic conditions, Oxford mandate stringency index scores, and percent fully vaccinated considered as statistical controls. Two multiple regression equations were computed with the 48 US contiguous states as analytic units. In Equation 1, the eight potential predictors of COVID-19 death rates other than Neuroticism were entered simultaneously on Step 1, and Neuroticism was entered on Step 2. In Equation 2, the SPSS 25 backward elimination procedure selected the nonredundant predictors from the block of eight in Step 1, and Neuroticism was entered on Step 2. Higher Neuroticism was associated with higher COVID-19 death rates in both equations. With all eight controls in Equation 1, Neuroticism still accounted for a significant 8.4% of the death rate variance. With the five nonredundant controls in Equation 2, Neuroticism accounted for 23.3%. Neuroticism had the largest β coefficient in each equation, .53 in Equation 1 and .58 in Equation 2. With redundant predictors eliminated in Equation 2, higher COVID-19 death rates also were associated with lower Oxford index scores, greater urbanisation, higher percent of population 65 and over, lower White percent, and lower percent fully vaccinated. Neither multicollinearity nor spatial autocorrelation was problematic. The state-level relations are *speculated* to stem from parallel individual-level underpinnings regarding the stress-prone Neurotic personality.

Keywords: COVID-19; mortality, stress; health; Big Five personality; geographical psychology

The 50 American states differed widely regarding the impact of COVID-19. For example, by February 27 of 2023, cumulative death rates per 100,000 persons ranged from 454 in Arizona to 129 in Hawaii (Statista, 2023). However, although there is a sizeable volume of studies focussed on the COVID-19 pandemic, almost none have explored the predictors of mortality with the states as the analytic units. A notable exception is the study by Doti (2021) who found temporally consistent evidence that higher death rates were associated with greater poverty and lower commitment to *mitigative* restrictions and mandates. Nevertheless, neither this state-level study nor any existing research with individuals as the analytic units has examined the possibility that dispositional factors may be related to death from COVID-19.

State-level research in this area is important. State governments are mainly responsible for pandemic and infectious disease information and alleviation efforts such as mask requirements, testing for infection, gathering size restrictions, cancellation of public events, and business closings. State populations also differ considerably on sociodemographic factors that may predispose residents to poorer health outcomes including death from COVID-19.

The present research examined the potential of Neuroticism from the Big Five personality model to predict COVID-19 death rates—to my knowledge, the first study to do so. The COVID-19 death rate in a state is operationally defined here as the number of deaths per 1,000,000 state population. The widely accepted Big Five model focusses on the major non-pathological personality dimensions—Openness to Experience, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Neuroticism, which appear to stem largely from genetic determinants (e.g., Costa & McCrae, 1995; John & Srivastava, 1999). State-level personality scores (Rentfrow et al., 2008) based on the responses of several hundred thousand state residents to the Big Five Inventory (John & Srivastava, 1999) are quite stable and have shown consistent temporal relations to a variety of state-level variables (e.g., Elleman et al., 2018). The state scores also have been successfully employed in research based on more recent years (e.g., Ebert et al., 2022; McCann, 2022, 2023a, 2024).

The characteristics of those high on Neuroticism seem most likely to increase the chances of contracting COVID-19. These features also would seem to make it more difficult to cope with the challenges of trying to recover from a life-threatening case. Persons nearer the high end of the Neuroticism dimension tend to be more anxious, moody, vulnerable, self-conscious, impulsive, depressed, tense, self-indulgent, envious, discontented, emotionally unstable, prone to nervousness, likely to be easily upset, likely to worry excessively, likely not to be relaxed, likely not to stay calm in strained situations, likely to harbour angry hostility, and likely to be poor stress managers (e.g., Costa & McCrae, 1995; John & Srivastava, 1999).

No published research could be located that has directly addressed the potential link between Neuroticism and dying from COVID-19 with either individuals or states as the analytic units. However, research indirectly suggests that it is quite plausible that being higher on Neuroticism may be associated with a greater tendency to contract and die from COVID-19 infection. For example, those higher on the Neuroticism dimension have been found to exhibit less support for government COVID-19 crisis management (De Coninck et al., 2020), to adhere less to government guidelines (Turk et al., 2021), to have more negative perceptions of daily life restrictions (Schmiedeberg & Thonnissen, 2021), to have lower rates of complying with governmental mandates to shelter-in-place (Gotz et al., 2021), and to take fewer pandemic precautions (Aschwanden et al., 2020). Those higher on Neuroticism also have been found to experience greater pandemic-related stress (Bellingtier et al., 2023), to be more likely to experience symptoms of acute stress disorder under COVID-19 quarantine in China (Chen et al., 2023), to be less resilient in the face of the pandemic and its restrictions (Kocjan et al., 2021), to show greater worry and accompanying negative affect concerning pandemic consequences (Kroencke et al., 2020), to be more likely to be infected by COVID-19 (Kanazawa, 2022), and to be more likely to require hospitalisation for COVID-19 (Batty et al., 2020). Therefore, given the research showing links between Neuroticism and factors that may be indirectly related to COVID-19 mortality, it appears that there may be a demonstrable association between being higher on Neuroticism and COVID-19 state death rates.

From a theoretical standpoint, there are several reasons to expect such a relation. For example, Segerstrom (2000) postulated links of Neuroticism to the immune system through its impacts on mood, life events, and health behaviours. Neurotic characteristics are likely to lead to negative moods with frequent regularity. It also is apparent that life events are shaped somewhat by Neurotic personality features. As well, those higher on Neuroticism would seem likely to engage in behaviours more detrimental than advantageous to health outcomes. Kern and Friedman (2011) also articulated various routes through which personality can influence health outcomes. They stated that personality “influences the habits we form, the behaviours we engage in, the relationships we develop, our appraisals and experience of stressful challenges, the situations we commonly choose, the reactions we invoke in others, and the lifelong pathways that we follow” (p. 84), and that these responses are related to the course of health practices and outcomes throughout a lifetime. Roberts et al. (2007) also asserted that personality may have effects on mortality because personality is related to pathogenetic mechanisms that have an impact on the course of disease and because personality differences may promote divergent reactions to the progression of disease. Again, persons higher on Neuroticism would seem more likely to negatively influence their health and eventually their longevity through these interrelated pathways.

Positions on certain personality dimensions are associated with unhealthy behaviours that ultimately lead to poorer health and shorter lives (e.g., Turiano et al., 2013). Personality also may be connected to longevity through genetic or physiological factors such as immunological functioning (e.g., Terracciano et al., 2008). Higher Neuroticism generally has been linked to poorer health and general disease level (e.g., Luo et al., 2023; Turiano et al., 2013), and shorter longevity (e.g., Terracciano et al., 2008; Turiano et al., 2013). The association between lower Neuroticism and higher longevity is thought to be in part based on the impact of Neuroticism on health risk behaviours (e.g., Terracciano et al., 2008). For example, a “metasynthesis” by Strickhouser et al. (2017) based on a secondary analysis of the results of previous meta-analytic studies found that the largest personality-health relations occurred for Neuroticism and although these relations were more prevalent regarding mental health outcomes, they did occur for health behaviours and physical health outcomes. As Wilson et al. (2004) concluded after finding that higher Neuroticism was associated with a greater number of deaths among 883 older Catholic clergy members followed for a mean of approximately five years, it appears that “neuroticism over a lifetime may compromise multiple physiological and functional systems and thereby increase vulnerability to disease in old age” (p. P114). In fact, Friedman et al. (1994) pointed out over 30 years ago that “when vulnerable people encounter psychosocial environments that are a poor match for their needs, chronic negative emotional patterns and unhealthy behavioral patterns often result” (p. 37). Therefore, the view is quite pervasive that higher Neuroticism is associated with having higher rates of health risk factors, greater susceptibility to disease, and elevated mortality in general, and consequently it is logical to assume that these relational dynamics also should apply to COVID-19 death rates in particular.

Stress appears to be at the core of the relation between Neuroticism and health outcomes, and that centrality may be expected to extend to COVID-19 mortality. Generally, the COVID-19 epidemic can be classified as a stressor for the American populace. However, as the transactional stress theory of Lazarus and Folkman (1984) asserts, individuals differ markedly in their perception of a challenging event or circumstance as a stressor, and consequently in the degree of stress that ensues. Stress theorists (e.g., Blascovich & Mendes, 2010; Crum et al., 2020; Lazarus & Folkman, 1984) commonly support the view that an individual’s perception and appraisal of a situation is critical to understanding whether an individual will experience stress from an encounter with such a situation (e.g., Hagger et al., 2020), and consequently whether the event will ultimately lead to poorer health outcomes. Neuroticism is strongly implicated in this process because more Neurotic persons have a greater tendency to perceive events in their lives as stressors (e.g., Da Silva Coelho et al., 2022; Ebstrup et al., 2011; Leger et al., 2016) and to react more strongly to those stressors (e.g., Hisler et al., 2020; Suls & Martin, 2005; Wrzus et al., 2021). In fact, Bellingtier et al. (2023) found that higher Neuroticism was associated with higher perceived stress irrespective of the COVID-19 events experienced that could have been interpreted as stressors, and Kroencke et al. (2020) found that higher Neuroticism was associated with greater worry and greater affective reactivity regarding COVID-19 pandemic consequences. One notable difference between COVID-19 mortality and all-

cause mortality is that the crisis climate of the pandemic was bound to spark increases in anxiety and stress in those most sensitive—the more neurotic.

It has long been known that an infectious disease can only develop if the person has been exposed to the infectious agent, but also that stress increases the risk that such exposure will lead to the actual contracting of the disease (e.g., Jemmott & Locke, 1984; Marsland et al., 2012; Pedersen et al., 2011). After conducting a review of the literature with the focus on the relation of negative events and affective states to the development of infectious disease, research by Cohen and Williamson (1991) showed that stressors cause negative affective states that have direct impacts on the immune system, as well as indirect impacts through the development of poor health behaviours that also decrease immunological defences. More recently, Lamontagne et al. (2021) reviewed “literature suggesting that chronic stress-induced hyperinflammation interacts synergistically with COVID-19-related inflammation, contributing to a potentially fatal cytokine storm syndrome” (p. 401), which implicates both chronic stress-induced and COVID-19-induced inflammation as contributors to heightened inflammation that is consistently found in COVID-19 cases and to hyperinflammation in those with an especially dire prognosis. Others have found that dispositional Neuroticism also is involved in the complex process underlying the relation between stress and infectious disease. Higher Neuroticism is associated with negative affect (e.g., Abbasi, 2016; Gniewosz, 2023; Abbasi et al., 2018), unhealthy behaviours (e.g., Allen et al., 2017; Krizan & Hisler, 2019; McCann, 2010), immune system deficiencies (e.g., Bouhuys et al., 2004; Gilbert et al., 1996; Stephan et al., 2023), and higher inflammation (e.g., Armon et al., 2013; Schmidt et al., 2018; Sutin et al., 2010).

Of course, other variables also have been suggested as factors associated with the tendency to contract COVID-19 and succumb to its effects. COVID-19 death rates tend to be higher the lower the SES (e.g., Hawkins et al., 2020), lower among Whites than Blacks (e.g., Sood & Sood, 2021), higher the greater the urbanisation (e.g., Ahmed et al., 2020), higher among those with greater general health risks (e.g., Williamson et al., 2020), higher among those 65 years of age and over (e.g., Amdaoud et al., 2021), higher among those with chronic conditions (e.g., Wang, Fang, et al., 2020), lower among those faced with greater COVID-19 restrictions and mandates (e.g., Doti, 2021), and lower among those vaccinated for the virus (e.g., Johnson et al., 2022). These eight factors and their subcomponents seem to constitute the most promising statistical controls regarding COVID-19 death rates.

The present study

The present research determined the extent to which state resident Neuroticism in the 48 contiguous states is related to state COVID-19 death rates. It focused exclusively on the 48 adjoining states for several reasons. In an epidemic with a virus that spreads through interpersonal contact and travel, there are far fewer such opportunities for transmission to the relatively remote states of Hawaii and Alaska. Hawaii also has by far the lowest White population percent and Alaska has the harshest northern climate, both factors that could influence the spread of COVID-19. As well, the nature of the spatial autocorrelation test and correction procedures require using only states that have borders with other states. The `R` `spdep` and `spatialreg` statistical packages (R, 2022) and the global Moran's *I* test to identify spatial autocorrelation (Anselin, 2003) necessitate the creation of a Queen's model binary “neighbourhood” matrix that categorises each state as a “neighbour” if its border touches that of another state at any point. Hawaii and Alaska are quite distant from each other and separated from the 48 contiguous states by the vastness of the Pacific Ocean and by Canada. Hawaii and Alaska have no such “neighbours” and consequently are unsuitable for placement in the “neighbourhood” matrix.

The present study considered the following eight variables primarily as statistical controls: SES, White population percent, urbanisation, estimates of general health risks, population percent 65 years of age and over, population percent over 65 experiencing at least four chronic conditions, state levels of the imposition of COVID-19 mandates, and population percent fully vaccinated for COVID-19. Previous studies have shown that each of these eight variables may be related to COVID-19 mortality (e.g., Ahmed et al., 2020; Amdaoud et al., 2021; Doti, 2021; Hawkins et al., 2020; Johnson et

al., 2022; Sood & Sood, 2021; Wang, Fang et al., 2020; Williamson et al., 2020). Some researchers also have reported that Neuroticism is related to SES (Luo et al., 2024), race (Johnson, 2000), urbanisation (Atherton et al., 2024), general health risks (Singh, 2023), age (Cukic & Weiss, 2014), chronic conditions (Weston et al., 2020), compliance with government COVID-19 mandates (Gotz et al., 2021), and chances of being vaccinated for COVID-19 (Zidkova et al., 2023). The eight variables were suitable as controls because each was potentially related to Neuroticism and to COVID-19 death rates—the two variables involved in the relation of prime interest in the current study.

METHODS

Measures

COVID-19 death rates. The cumulative COVID-19 state death rates reported as the number per million state population as of December 10, 2021, were taken from KFF (2021a).

Neuroticism. Rentfrow et al. (2008) computed state Neuroticism z scores based on 619,397 internet survey respondents across the 50 states and Washington, DC, to the 44-item Big Five Inventory (John & Srivastava, 1999) between December of 1999 and January of 2005. Neuroticism had a mean inter-subsample correlation of .85 based on three random subsamples and a high test-retest correlation of .86 based on two temporal subsamples. The Neuroticism state-level and individual-level factor structure had a congruence coefficient of .95. The developers also reported that the respondent sample was reasonably representative according to census data even though it was somewhat younger than the general population and tended to over represent members of the middle class.

SES. State SES was based on four variables—per capita personal income, percent of individuals living below the poverty line, percent of persons 25 years of age and over with at least high school graduation, and percent of persons 25 years of age and over with at least a bachelor's degree. Per capita personal income in 2020 was obtained from FRED (2022). Poverty line data for 2019 were provided by KFF (2022). High school graduation and bachelor's degree data were provided for 2018 by the U.S. Census Bureau (2022). Poverty line scores for 2019 were reverse scored (i.e., multiplied by -1) before further computations. The four SES components then were standardised, summed for each state, and the results were standardised. Higher scores indicate higher SES. Cronbach alpha reliability for the resulting composite is .88.

White population percent. The 2021 White population percent for each of the 48 contiguous states was taken from KFF (2023).

Urban population percent. The U.S. Census Bureau (2023) provided the 2020 urban population percent for each state.

Percent of at-risk adults. The percent of each state's population aged 18 years and older having a greater risk of serious illness if infected with COVID-19 was taken from KFF (2021b). Data were based on 2018 BRFSS data concerning medical conditions such as diabetes, heart disease, lung disease, and obesity. Those in nursing homes and other institutional settings were excluded.

Percent of population 65 and over. The percent of each state population 65 and older based on 2019 data was taken from ACL (2021).

Older adult chronic conditions. The percent of Medicare beneficiaries at least 65 years of age in each state with at least four chronic conditions was obtained from the Senior Report released by the United Health Foundation (2022). They based their state values on 2018 data from several different sources.

Oxford mandate stringency index for 2020. Information regarding the Oxford index as used in the present study was provided by Doti (2021). The index assesses the existence of 11 state responses to COVID-19: school closings, workplace closings, cancellation of public events, gathering size restrictions, public transit closures, and requirements to stay at home, internal movement

restrictions, international travel restrictions, public information campaigns, testing policies, and contact tracing (Doti, 2021, pp. 32–33). The scores used here were based on the mean daily scores from January 1 to December 1 in 2020 (Doti, 2021, pp. 37–38). Scores can potentially range from 0 to 100. Higher scores indicate greater mandate and restriction stringency.

Percent fully vaccinated. The percent in each state fully vaccinated for COVID-19 as of December 3 of 2021 was obtained from KFF (2021c).

Analytical strategy

Following the computation of descriptive statistics and Pearson correlations, two multiple regression equations were computed. In Equation 1, the eight potential predictors of COVID-19 death rates other than Neuroticism were entered simultaneously on Step 1, and Neuroticism was entered on Step 2. In Equation 2, the “backward” elimination procedure in SPSS 27 was used to select non-redundant predictors from the block of eight in Step 1, and Neuroticism was entered on Step 2. Equation 2 was designated the final predictor model. In addition, the nine potential predictors were tested for multicollinearity and each regression equation was tested for the existence of spatial autocorrelation using R (R, 2022). All significance tests were two-tailed with an alpha level of .05.

RESULTS

Means, standard deviations, and Pearson correlations for the 48 adjoining states are displayed in Table 1. Most notably, state COVID-19 death rates correlated significantly with Neuroticism (.39), SES (–.56), White population percent (–.34), percent of at-risk adults (.37), older adult chronic conditions (.61), and percent fully vaccinated (–.46). Exploratory computations also showed that COVID-19 death rates did not significantly correlate with the other four Big Five personality variables: Openness to Experience (–.22), Conscientiousness (.09), Extraversion (.18), and Agreeableness (–.11).

Multiple regression results are presented in Table 2. On Step 1 of multiple regression Equation 1, the eight predictors together accounted for 65.1% of the state death rate variance, $F(8, 39) = 9.11, p < .001$. On Step 2, Neuroticism accounted for a further 8.4%, $F(1, 38) = 12.01, p < .001$. The significant standardised regression coefficients (β s) were .48 for percent of population 65 and over, –.30 for the Oxford mandate stringency index, –.53 for percent fully vaccinated, and .53 for Neuroticism.

On Step 1 of Equation 2 using the backward elimination procedure, White population percent, urban population percent, percent of population 65 and over, Oxford mandate stringency index, and percent fully vaccinated were retained. They accounted for 48.5% of the variance, $F(5, 42) = 7.91, p < .001$. However, Neuroticism still accounted for an additional 23.3%, $F(1, 41) = 33.78, p < .001$. The significant β s were –.41 for White population percent, .34 for urban population percent, .26 for percent of population 65 and over, –.38 for the Oxford mandate stringency index, –.42 for percent fully vaccinated, and .58 for Neuroticism.

Regarding multicollinearity, the only one of the nine predictors to have a VIF of over 10 was percent of at-risk adults with a value of 13.67. Regorz (2020) recommends that is not necessary to look at SPSS collinearity diagnostics unless there are more than two predictors with VIFs over the threshold. Furthermore, when Equation 2 was recomputed in exploratory fashion excluding the percent at-risk variable, results were identical to those of the original equation.

The R spdep, spatialreg, and haven statistical packages (R, 2022) were used to assess the potential impacts of spatial autocorrelation on the two multiple regression equations in Table 2. The global Moran’s I test was employed to identify spatial autocorrelation of residuals (Anselin, 2003). A Queen’s model binary neighbourhood matrix was created that categorised each state that touched another state at any point as a “neighbour” of that state using “1” and “0” dummy coding. To facilitate the analyses in R, an additional main data matrix was created in which the variables involved in the regression equations were standardised. If the Moran’s I statistic standard deviate was significant, a spatial lag regression model was computed with the lagsarlm function of the spatialreg

package. This R procedure uses standard simultaneous regression equations. Therefore, for the two original equations, the relevant variables were entered as a block.

Spatial autocorrelation results in Table 3 show that Moran's I statistic standard deviate was 4.17 ($p < .001$) for Equation 1 and 4.80 ($p < .001$) for Equation 2. However, the direction and magnitude of the β coefficients with spatial lag control remained extremely close to the original values for each equation. The largest substantive change occurred when the β for urban population percent in Equation 1 increased from a nonsignificant .27 to a significant .30. For Equation 1, the β for Neuroticism increased only from .53 to .55 in the spatial lag model. For Equation 2, the β for Neuroticism decreased marginally from .58 to .53 in the lag model. Therefore, it was concluded that no substantive qualifications were necessary, and that the full interpretation could be based on the two original ordinary least squares (OLS) equations.

DISCUSSION

The present study yielded a final predictor model for state COVID-19 death rates that included six independent predictors. Higher death rates were associated with higher state resident Neuroticism. Higher death rates also were associated with lower White population percent, higher urban population percent, higher percent of the population 65 and over, lower Oxford mandate stringency scores, and lower percent of the population fully vaccinated.

The Big Five Neuroticism dimension clearly demonstrated its worth as a predictor in this context. It correlated significantly with death rates ($r = .39$). It also had significant positive β s of .53 and .58 in the two multiple regression equations—the largest of any predictor in each equation. As well, with all other non-redundant predictors statistically controlled in the final regression model, Neuroticism still accounted for another 23.3% of the COVID-19 state death rate variance.

The current analytic procedures allowed predictors that showed no significant Pearson correlation with death rates to enter a final regression model when previously entered predictors reduced the criterion variance yet to be explained. The procedures also sometimes prevented predictors that did show a significant Pearson correlation with death rates from entering the final equation because it already included correlated predictors that essentially served as covariates. These statistical control effects emphasise the cautious interpretation that is necessary whenever researchers examine only a single potential predictor or a small group of potential predictors of death from COVID-19 infection.

Some of the findings of the present research corroborate the state-level conclusions of Doti (2021). As in the present study, Doti found multiple regression evidence that higher scores on the Oxford mandate stringency index were associated with lower death rates. He also found that higher poverty was associated with higher death rates. Poverty was not included as a separate variable in the present analysis, but state poverty rate was included as one of the four components of the composite SES variable. The Pearson correlation was $-.56$ between COVID-19 death rates and SES. However, with the other eight potential predictors statistically controlled in the multiple regression, the β of $-.25$ for SES was not significant, and in the backward elimination equation, SES was not retained as a predictor.

All variables in the present research were established on state-aggregated data. Therefore, the results logically apply to the 48 contiguous states rather than individuals. Geographical psychology proponents (e.g., Rentfrow, 2010; Rentfrow, 2014; Rentfrow & Gosling, 2021; Rentfrow et al., 2008; Rentfrow & Jokela, 2016, 2019) are fully aware of inherent fallibilities in cross-level generalisations such as the “compositional fallacy” (Pettigrew, 1997) which occurs when individual-level results are assumed to generalise to the aggregate level and the “ecological fallacy” (Robinson, 1950) which

Table 1

Means, standard deviations, and Pearson Correlations

Variables	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1. COVID-19 death rates	2343.40	654.05									
2. Neuroticism	.05	1.01	.39**								
3. SES	.00	1.00	-.56***	-.24							
4. White population percent	67.43	14.50	-.34*	.05	.23						
5. Urban population percent	72.31	14.96	.10	-.22	.29*	-.64***					
6. Percent of at-risk adults	38.31	3.64	.37*	.58***	-.67***	.20	-.53***				
7. Percent of population 65 and over	17.02	1.83	.01	.40**	-.01	.36*	-.42**	.63***			
8. Older adult chronic conditions	38.79	6.22	.61***	.61***	-.46***	-.35*	.16	.51***	.04		
9. Oxford mandate stringency index	41.09	8.02	-.22	.38**	.17	-.28	.24	.03	.21	.06	
10. Percent fully vaccinated	57.91	8.09	-.46***	.11	.68***	-.13	.34*	-.33*	.21	-.12	.61***

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$. Two-tailed tests.

Table 2
 Multiple Regression Equations Using Simultaneous and Backward Elimination Procedures to Determine Significant Independent Predictors of COVID-19 State Death Rates

Equation	Step	Entry method	Predictors	<i>df</i>	<i>R</i> ² change	<i>F</i>	Predictor β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
1	1	simultaneous	SES	8, 39	.651	9.11***	-.25	-1.02	.313
			White population percent				-.29	-1.72	.094
			Urban population percent				.27	1.75	.089
			Percent of at-risk adults				-.48	-1.57	.125
			Percent of population 65 and over				.48	2.66	.011
			Older adult chronic conditions				.21	1.11	.274
			Oxford mandate stringency index				-.30	-2.16	.037
			Percent fully vaccinated				-.53	-2.97	.005
2	2	forced	Neuroticism	1, 38	.084	12.01***	.53	3.47	.001
2	1	backward elimination	White population percent	5, 42	.485	7.91***	-.41	-3.57	.001
			Urban population percent				.34	2.67	.011
			Percent of population 65 and over				.26	2.43	.019
			Oxford mandate stringency index				-.38	-3.12	.003
			Percent fully vaccinated				-.52	-4.41	.001
			Neuroticism				-.52	-4.41	.001
2	2	forced	Neuroticism	1, 41	.233	33.78***	.58	5.81	.001

p* < .05. *p* < .01. ****p* < .001. Two-tailed tests.

Table 3

Spatial Autocorrelation Results for the Multiple Regression Equations in Table 2

Equation	Moran's I ^a	Original regression equation		Spatial lag equation	
		Predictors (if significant Moran's I)	β	β	Rho
1	4.17***	SES	-.25	-.23	.25
		White population percent	-.29	-.27	
		Urban population percent	.27	.30*	
		Percent of at-risk adults	-.48	-.45	
		Percent of population 65 and over	.48*	.49**	
		Older adult chronic conditions	.21	.11	
		Oxford mandate stringency index	-.30*	-.31**	
		Percent fully vaccinated	-.53**	-.51***	
		Neuroticism	.53***	.55***	
2	4.80***	White population percent	-.41***	-.36***	.24
		Urban population percent	.34*	.33**	
		Percent of population 65 and over	.26*	.27**	
		Oxford mandate stringency index	-.38**	-.35***	
		Percent fully vaccinated	-.52***	-.49***	
		Neuroticism	.58***	.53***	

^aMoran's I statistic standard deviate.

*p < .05. **p < .01. ***p < .001. Two-tailed tests.

occurs when aggregate-level relations are assumed to generalise to the individual level. Nevertheless, proponents also maintain that wise and cautious extrapolation in concert with supportive empirical evidence can be employed fruitfully to speculatively deduce possible implications for aggregate-level associations from individual-level processes and vice versa. To Ebert et al. (2021), "personality traits constitute meaningful constructs not only on the individual level but also at the level of geographic units" (p. 379). Therefore, the current state-level relations are speculated to have parallel individual-level underpinnings. However, due caution must be exercised in making any cross-level extrapolative interpretations based solely on the present results.

In line with the focus on Neuroticism, it is speculated here that the reported state-level relations are grounded in state-accumulated individual associations involving higher Neuroticism, elevated stress based on more threatening perceptions of COVID-19, higher negative affect, stress-induced deficiencies in effective immunologic responding, heightened inflammation, a propensity toward the adoption of unhealthy behaviours, increased chances of contracting COVID-19, and ultimately a greater likelihood of dying with COVID-19. As reported earlier in this article, except for the relation of Neuroticism to the chances of dying with COVID-19 which has received support with states as the analytic units in the present research, Neuroticism has been found to relate positively to each of these six other outcome variables (e.g., Bellingtier et al., 2023; Gilbert et al., 1996; Kanazawa, 2022; Krizan & Hisler, 2019; Kroencke et al., 2020; Schmidt et al., 2018) using individuals as the analytic units. Therefore, the path from Neuroticism to COVID-19 to death at the individual level is plausible and most of the sections of the path have received at least some empirical support. However, no reliable individual-level research directly supporting the final section of the path culminating in death is likely to surface regarding the recent COVID-19 pandemic—for obvious reasons.

In summary, it can be speculated that persons with higher Neuroticism levels perceive higher degrees of stress in their lives (e.g., Ebstrup et al., 2011), react more strongly to perceived stressors (e.g., Suls & Martin, 2005), and experience greater negative affect in response to those stressors (e.g., Abbasi et al., 2018). It can be further speculated that cumulative negative affect is associated with immunological deficiencies (e.g., Cohen & Williamson, 1991) and heightened inflammatory responses (e.g., Graham-Engeland et al., 2018) that contribute to deteriorating health (e.g., McClendon et al., 2021) and premature mortality (e.g., Hall et al., 2015). These stress-related processes clearly may pertain to COVID-19. Those with higher Neuroticism levels may have been more likely to ultimately succumb to COVID-19 infection because of their general life history regarding the experience and perception of stressors coupled with the perceived threats and stressors specifically linked to the COVID-19 pandemic. Mortality from other causes has been associated with higher perceived stress

(e.g., Bregola et al., 2022), a more pronounced experience of stressors and greater negative affect response (e.g., Chiang et al., 2018), elevated immunological deficiencies (e.g., Xia et al., 2023), and increased inflammation (e.g., Cribb et al., 2022). COVID-19 deaths may have followed the same stress-related path, and that path may strongly implicate dispositional Neuroticism as a foundational factor.

The view that responses to the pandemic were related to political orientation pervaded public and social media. The general theme was that Democrats were more responsive than Republicans to COVID-19 mitigation efforts. If this were true, then COVID-19 rates of death should have been lower in populations preferring Democrat rather than Republican politicians and policies. As the pandemic progressed, evidence shifted to seemingly support that expectation. For example, states led by Republican governors “had fewer per capita COVID-19 cases, deaths, and positive tests early in the pandemic, but these trends reversed in early May 2020 (positive tests), June 2020 (cases), and July 2020 (deaths)” (Neelon et al., 2021, p. 118). Chen and Karim (2022) reported a similar pattern with American counties as the units of analysis. Not only may state political orientation have been related to government policies and actions regarding the COVID-19 pandemic and resident reactions to those provisions, conservative political leaning also has been shown to be associated with lower Neuroticism at the state level (e.g., McCann, 2014a, 2014b). This issue was explored using the data of the present study and the percent of the popular vote for Biden in 2020 (Leip, 2024). The Biden vote correlated a significant $-.35$ with COVID-19 death rates. However, an exploratory partial correlation with the Biden percent of the popular vote as the lone statistical control revealed that the correlation between Neuroticism and state COVID-19 death rates actually rose from $.39$ to $.46$. In other words, it appears that state political preference probably had little impact on the relations found in the present research.

Some readers also might wonder whether state differences in health care provision and access could have had an impact on the present results showing a relation between Neuroticism and COVID-19 death rates. There is some limited evidence that aspects of higher clinical care quality were associated with lower COVID-19 mortality (e.g., Kunz & Popper, 2020; Magesh et al., 2021; Tchicaya et al., 2021). Nevertheless, an empirical answer to this question also was sought through exploratory analyses using the data of the present research. America’s Health Rankings (2021) provided state values for public health funding per capita based on data for 2019 and 2020, the number of primary health care providers in 2021, and the percentage of adults who avoided seeing a doctor because of costs in the past 12 months as assessed in 2020. Death rates correlated a significant $.42$ with avoiding health care due to cost and Neuroticism correlated a significant $.32$ with the number of health care providers per capita. These were the only significant correlations. A partial correlation with all three health care variables as the only statistical controls produced a correlation of $.44$ between Neuroticism and COVID-19 death rates compared to the original correlation of $.39$. Partial correlations controlling for each of the three variables separately yielded substantively the same results. It appears from this cursory examination that health access and public health funding could not contribute to an explanation of the pattern of findings in the present study.

Limitations and issues

Although some readers may at first consider the sample size inadequate for inferential statistics, extenuating circumstances lead to the rejection of this notion. The fundamental use of inferential statistics is to establish the probability that the results of sample data analysis should also apply to the population that produced the sample. However, the current isometric sample-population context effectively negates the need to make such inferences. Nevertheless, the making of analytical decisions and the drawing of conclusions did utilise statistical significance tests in this study. A lower sample size does decrease the chances of a relation being statistically significant, but expected relations emerged here that were statistically significant despite such restriction. Furthermore, researchers often have successfully conducted analyses using this analytical tack with such small samples in the past (e.g., Barber, 2015; McCann, 2008, 2017, 2019, 2021b, 2023a, 2023b; Simonton, 2006).

The present correlation and multiple regression analysis is built upon cross-sectional correlations between variables. Consequently, it does not logically permit the drawing of causal inferences based on the statistical results, which constitutes a limitation of the current study. However, it can be speculated that certain causal directions are more likely than others. For example, it seems obvious that COVID-19 death rates do not cause the assessed state differences on variables such as Neuroticism, White population percent, or higher urbanisation. It also seems evident that genetically influenced dispositional variables are foundational in a population, and that it is reasonable to speculate that they can lead to state-level differences in risk-factor variables. It also seems that such postulated causal connections ultimately will remain speculative because personality variables simply cannot be randomly assigned to persons to serve as independent variables in a true experiment, the research tool that provides the most confident causal deduction. Quasi-experimental and prospective longitudinal designs generally may be seen as a second-level strategy to deduce causality, but no such research is likely to surface directly pertaining to the present research context—for obvious reasons. Nevertheless, perhaps such longitudinal approaches incorporating variables similar to those in the current study but focused on other infectious diseases and their resulting mortality could promote further understanding of the dynamics that may be involved.

Some readers also might be concerned that the state-level assessment of Neuroticism conducted from 1999 to 2005 by Rentfrow et al. (2008) is temporally discrepant from the other variables which were based largely on the years from 2018 to 2021. However, the fact that state personality is unlikely to have changed much over this time span should allay concern about this lack of congruence. For example, Elleman et al. (2018) have shown that such state-level personality scores are temporally stable and have provided consistent relations to a variety of sociodemographic variables over the years they examined – 1999 through 2015. As well, these state scores have been employed fruitfully in various research contexts often pertaining to more recent years (e.g., Ebert et al., 2022; McCann, 2022, 2023a; Obschonka et al., 2013; Pesta et al., 2012). Although the developers of the state-level Neuroticism scores reported that respondents to the Big Five measure were quite representative according to census data but were somewhat younger than the general population and drawn disproportionately from the middle class, these were the best available state Neuroticism scores. In a sense, they also proved their worth by providing meaningful statistical results in the present study.

Readers should note too that the state-level variables analyzed in the present research were based on the behaviors and responses of individuals, but the original data development processes aggregated the data at the level of the state. Therefore, the present results properly pertain to states rather than to individuals. Without sufficient empirical evidence of parallel relations occurring at the state level and the individual level, there are inherent risks in cross-level extrapolations (e.g., Pettigrew, 1997; Robinson, 1950). One cannot simply assume that such extrapolations are valid. Researchers have conducted relatively few corresponding analyses at the individual level that can corroborate the present state-level relations. Nevertheless, there is plausible reason to speculatively assume that the current demonstrated state-level relations result from the accumulation of parallel individual-level relations. Nevertheless, more adequate and comprehensive evidence obtained through research with individuals as the analytic units is necessary to bolster confidence in such postulations.

Of course, readers also should recognise that the veracity of the present results ultimately depends upon the validity of the state death rates as operationally defined here. There is a degree of continuing controversy surrounding these measures regarding their accuracy and meaning within the context of the COVID-19 pandemic (e.g., Mathieu et al., 2020). For example, there was some suspicion at the time that some persons categorised as “dying from COVID-19” actually “died with COVID-19” because other concurrent health factors caused their deaths. Readers should have confidence in the present analyses and the obtained results. However, they also should be cautiously aware of potential inaccuracies in the COVID-19 death rate data.

Regarding generalisability, it is speculated that Neuroticism would show a similar relation to COVID-19 death rates in other studies similar to the present one in countries in which similar data are available and there is a sufficient number of geographically based political administrative units on which to conduct such an aggregate-level analysis, such as the Local Authority Districts (LADS) of the

United Kingdom. It also is speculated that the relation exists with individuals as the units of analysis, although it would be difficult to verify because of an understandable lack of critical data regarding Neuroticism and COVID-19 deaths based on the same persons. As well, it is speculated that a similar relation exists between Neuroticism and death resulting from other infectious diseases and chronic conditions at the individual and the aggregate level of analysis. Of course, some research already exists with individuals as the analytic units (e.g., Butler et al., 2023; Shipley et al., 2007; Zhang et al., 2022) and with American states as the units of analysis (e.g., McCann, 2014c, 2020, 2021a) showing that Neuroticism is related to being susceptible to certain chronic diseases and to mortality from those conditions.

Potential applied implications

State resident standing on the Neuroticism dimension is an important predictor of state COVID-19 death rates in the current study. However, state resident Neuroticism also is important for other relations in the reported results. For example, state residents having a higher risk of serious illness if infected with COVID-19 based on a composite at-risk index (KFF, 2021b) also is substantially associated with state residents being higher on Neuroticism even when those in nursing homes and other institutional settings are excluded. But this at-risk index also is positively correlated with COVID-19 death rates, and an exploratory partial correlation shows that this relation was reduced from .37 to a nonsignificant .19 when Neuroticism was controlled. As well, an exploratory partial correlation showed that the correlation between the Oxford mandate stringency index and COVID-19 death rates increased significantly from a nonsignificant -.22 to a significant -.43 when Neuroticism was controlled. In retrospect, it would seem to have been advantageous if several COVID-19 policies and actions had been somewhat tailored to the mean level of Neuroticism among state residents.

However, it is also important to note that some of the present research results and attendant speculations pertain to relatively immutable variables. Offering effective applications based on remedies involving planned modifications of such a risk factor as Neuroticism is not a realistic option because it is largely genetically determined, firmly an integral part of the person, and quite stable throughout life. However, it still would seem prudent in policy and practice to consider a tailoring process regarding the modal characteristics of states on such a variable when designing information appeals for precautions and practices pertaining to pandemics and more limited outbreaks of infectious diseases. For example, Olsacher et al. (2023) have reported on the effectiveness of such a tailoring approach based on the Big Five to encourage organ donation in Germany and Kim et al. (2023) have proposed such a tailoring model for the Big Five and the provision of optimal health care. Of course, other results of the present research suggest that instituting state factors such as those gauged by the Oxford mandate stringency index or the provision of suitable vaccines should reduce future negative health outcomes such as mortality, but these factors also should be more effective if appeals and incentives for compliance are put in place with due regard to state resident levels of Neuroticism and the attendant proclivities and emotional responses likely to accompany those differing levels of Neuroticism.

Future research

There are several avenues of research that could prove beneficial to further understanding and perhaps eventually lead to novel applications regarding future infectious disease threats. For example, researchers evidently have not used COVID-19 fatality rates as an outcome variable with states as the analytic units. This is a somewhat different mortality measure worthy of investigation. The COVID-19 fatality rate in a state is the number of such deaths divided by the total number of confirmed COVID-19 cases in a state. Unlike death rates as used in the present study, the denominator for the computation of fatality rates is based only on the portion of the state population infected with COVID-19. Unfortunately, while counts of COVID-19 deaths may be relatively reliable from state to state, estimates of state infections are much less reliable as a denominator for such computations than are whole state populations. Confirmation of state COVID-19 infection depends upon COVID-19 tests, but the percent of a population tested varied greatly from state to state and those tested were either voluntarily self-selected or persons who had taken the test once the presence of COVID-19 had

been suspected. To compound the problem, state populations differed widely in their attitudes toward the pandemic, whether it was wise to be vaccinated for COVID-19, and whether pandemic restrictions should be followed or even put in place. Although challenging, the results of this line of research also could enhance our understanding of the dynamics and outcomes of the COVID-19 pandemic and perhaps outbreaks of other infectious diseases.

The present research found that state White population percent correlated significantly in a negative direction with COVID-19 death rates. However, there is a possibility that the four major race categories in the USA—White, Black, Hispanic, and Asian—may have shown different rates of mortality during the pandemic. It is generally reported that higher COVID-19 death rates were associated with being Black (e.g., CDC, 2022; Gawthrop, 2022; Golestaneh et al., 2020; Poulson et al., 2021; Shannon et al., 2022; Sood & Sood, 2021) but exceptions exist (e.g., Jacobson et al., 2021). Researchers also have reported that Hispanics died from COVID-19 at a higher rate than Whites (e.g., CDC, 2022; Cheng et al., 2020; Jacobson et al., 2021; Mackey et al., 2021), but contrary results also exist (e.g., Gawthrop, 2022). As well, research has often showed that Asians had a lower chance of dying from COVID-19 than Whites (e.g., CDC, 2022; Mackey et al., 2021), but some also have reported that Asians died at a higher rate than Whites (e.g., Wang, Gee, et al., 2020; Yan et al., 2021; Yee, 2021). A comprehensive examination of the relation of racial/ethnic variables to COVID-19 mortality with states as the analytic units in a similar methodological context to that of the present study also would appear to be fertile ground for future research.

In another research vein, a recent study by Peters et al. (2022) in part used specification curve analyses to test the relation of the Big Five to COVID-19 cumulative infection and death rates from April 15 to September 30 of 2020 in 2,366 counties of the USA while controlling for a relatively large set of other potential predictors. There was some evidence that COVID-19 death rates were negatively associated with Neuroticism. These results generally are contrary to what was found in the present study, in which Neuroticism showed a positive association with COVID-19 death rates. Reasons for the difference between the two studies in direction for the association between Neuroticism and death rates is unknown. However, one possibility is that the data for the study by Peters et al. (2022) was collected only up to the end of September of 2020 while the data for the present research was based on death rate data up to December 10 of 2021. For example, Doti (2021) found differences in the relations of predictors to COVID-19 mortality between data for the first half and the second half of 2020. Further research could be initiated to formally address why the relational directions are discrepant between the present state-level research and the county-level study by Peters et al. (2022).

In the interest of cross-cultural generalisation, it also would be useful to examine the extent to which the pattern of the present results applies to other countries and to their internal geographically defined administrative units. For instance, the UK has readily available Big Five personality scores for 380 local authority districts (LADs; Rentfrow et al., 2015). Data for COVID-19 death rates and other appropriate variables also are likely to be obtainable from various UK sources. Therefore, a cross-cultural UK replication of the present study seems feasible using LADS as the analytic units. Other nations also may provide such replication opportunities.

CONCLUSION

The psychological dynamics of personality and stress, especially those highlighting the importance of Neuroticism – which was not surpassed in β weight magnitude by any of the other predictors in this study, deserve much more attention within this research context. So do the underlying processes through which race, urbanization, age, and various pandemic mitigation efforts may exercise their influence. Future studies with individuals, aggregate divisions such as states and counties, and comparable analyses in other nations, hold promise to further our understanding and to help formulate more effective responses to future pandemics, epidemics, and other more isolated outbreaks of infectious diseases.

Acknowledgements: None declared

Conflict of interests: None declared

Funding: None declared

Ethical approval: Not applicable

REFERENCES

- Abbasi, I. S. (2016). The role of neuroticism in the maintenance of chronic baseline stress perception and negative affect. *The Spanish Journal of Psychology*, 19, E9.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/sjp.2016.9>
- Abbasi, I. S., Rattan, N., Kousar, T., & Elsayed, F. K. (2018). Neuroticism and close relationships: How negative affect is linked with relationship disaffection in couples. *American Journal of Family Therapy*, 46(2), 139–152. <http://dx.doi.org.cbu.idm.oclc.org/10.1080/01926187.2018.1461030>
- ACL. (2021). *2020 profile of older Americans*. Administration for Community Living, U.S. Department of Health and Human Services.
https://acl.gov/sites/default/files/Aging%20and%20Disability%20in%20America/2020ProfileOlderAmericans.Final_.pdf
- Ahmed, R., Williamson, M., Hamid, M. A., & Ashraf, N. (2020). United States county-level COVID-19 death rates and case fatality rates vary by region and urban status. *Healthcare*, 8(3), 330–341.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare8030330>
- Allen, M. S., Walter, E. E., & McDermott, M. S. (2017). Personality and sedentary behavior: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Health Psychology*, 36(3), 255–263.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/hea0000429>
- Amdaoud, M., Arcuri, G., & Levratto, N. (2021). Are regions equal in adversity? A spatial analysis of spread and dynamics of COVID-19 in Europe. *European Journal of Health Economics*, 22(4), 629–642. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10198-021-01280-6>
- America's Health Rankings. (2021). *Annual report 2021*. America's Health Rankings, United Health Foundation.
<https://assets.americashealthrankings.org/app/uploads/americashealthrankings-2021annualreport.pdf>
- Anselin, L. (2003). *An introduction to spatial regression analysis in R*.
<https://labs.bio.unc.edu/buckley/documents/anselinintrospatregres.pdf>
- Armon, G., Melamed, S., Shirom, A., Berliner, S., & Shapira, I. (2013). The associations of the five factor model of personality with inflammatory biomarkers: A four-year prospective study. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 54(6), 750–755.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2012.11.035>
- Aschwanden, D., Strickhouser, J. E., Sesker, A. A., Lee, J. H., Luchetti, M., Stephan, Y., Sutin, A. R., & Terracciano, A. (2021). Psychological and behavioural responses to coronavirus disease 2019: The role of personality. *European Journal of Personality*, 35(1), 51–66.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/per.2281>
- Atherton, O. E., Willroth, E. C., Graham, E. K., Luo, J., Mroczek, D. K., & Lewis-Thames, M. W. (2024). Rural-urban differences in personality traits and well-being in adulthood. *Journal of Personality*, 92(1), 73–87. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jopy.12818>
- Barber, N. (2015). Why is Mississippi more religious than New Hampshire? Maternal security and ethnicity as factors. *Cross-Cultural Research*, 49, 315–325.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1069397114556071>
- Batty, G. D., Deary, I. J., Luciano, M., Altschul, D. M., Kivimaki, M., & Gale, C. R. (2020). Psychosocial factors and hospitalisations for COVID-19: Prospective cohort study based on a community sample. *Brain, Behavior, and Immunity*, 89, 569–578. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbi.2020.06.021>
- Bellingtier, J. A., Mund, M., & Wrzus, C. (2023). The role of extraversion and neuroticism for experiencing stress during the third wave of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Current Psychology*, 42, 12202–12212. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-021-02600-y>
- Blascovich, J., & Mendes, W. B. (2010). Social psychophysiology and embodiment. In S. T. Fiske, D. T. Gilbert, & G. Lindzey (Eds.), *The handbook of social psychology* (5th ed., pp. 194–227). Wiley.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470561119.socpsy001006>
- Bouhuys, A. L., Flentge, F., Oldehinkel, A. J., & van den Berg, M. D. (2004). Potential psychosocial mechanisms linking depression to immune function in elderly subjects. *Psychiatry Research*, 127(3), 237–245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2004.05.001>
- Bregola, A. G., Ottaviani, A. C., Luchesi, B. M., & Pavarini, S. C. L. (2022). Accumulated cognitive impairment, frailty, burden, and perceived stress and the risk of hospitalization and

- mortality in older caregivers. *Dementia & Neuropsychologia*, 16(1), 33–44.
<https://doi.org/10.1590/1980-5764-dn-2020-0091>
- Butler, M., Turiano, N., Buckley, L., McGeehan, M., & O'Suilleabhain, P. S. (2023). Neuroticism facets and mortality risk in adulthood: A systematic review and narrative synthesis. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research*, 175, ArtID: 111500. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychores.2023.111500>
- CDC. (2022, July 28). Risk for COVID-19 infection, hospitalization, and death by race/ethnicity. *Centers for Disease Control and Prevention*. <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/covid-data/investigations-discovery/hospitalization-death-by-race-ethnicity.html>
- Chen, H.-F., & Karim, S. A. (2022). Relationship between political partisanship and COVID-19 deaths: Future implications for public health. *Journal of Public Health (Oxford)*, 44(3), 716–723.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/pubmed/fdab136>
- Cheng, K. J. G., Sun, Y., & Monnat, S. M. (2020). COVID-19 death rates are higher in rural counties with larger shares of Blacks and Hispanics. *Journal of Rural Health*, 36(4), 602–608.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/jrh.12511>
- Chiang, J. J., Turiano, N. A., Mroczek, D. K., & Miller, G. E. (2018). Affective reactivity to daily stress and 20-year mortality risk in adults with chronic illness: Findings from the National Study of Daily Experiences. *Health Psychology*, 37(2), 170–178. <https://doi.org/10.1037/hea0000567>
- Da Silva Coelho, C., Joly-Burra, E., Ihle, A., Ballhausen, N., Haas, M., Hering, A., Künzi, M., Laera, G., Miknevičute, G., Tinello, D., & Kliegel, M. (2021). Higher levels of neuroticism in older adults predict lower executive functioning across time: The mediating role of perceived stress. *European Journal of Ageing*, 20(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10433-021-00665-z>
- Cohen, S., & Williamson, G. M. (1991). Stress and infectious disease in humans. *Psychological Bulletin*, 109(1), 5–24. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.109.1.5>
- Costa, P. T., & McCrae, R. R. (1995). Domains and facets: Hierarchical personality assessment using the Revised NEO Personality Inventory. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 64(1), 21–50.
https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327752jpa6401_2
- Cribb, L., Hodge, A. M., Yu, C., Li, S. X., English, D. R., Makalic, E., Southey, M. C., Milne, R. L., Giles, G. G., & Dugué, P. A. (2022). Inflammation and epigenetic aging are largely independent markers of biological aging and mortality. *The Journals of Gerontology: Series A*, 77(12), 2378–2386.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/gerona/glac091>
- Crum, A. J., Jamieson, J. P., & Akinola, M. (2020). Optimizing stress: An integrated intervention for regulating stress responses. *Emotion*, 20(1), 120–125. <https://doi.org/10.1037/emo0000670>
- Cukic, I., & Weiss, A. (2014). Personality and diabetes mellitus incidence in a national sample. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research*, 77(3), 163–168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychores.2014.07.004>
- De Coninck, D., d'Haenens, L., & Matthijs, K. (2020). Perceived vulnerability to disease and attitudes towards public health measures: COVID-19 in Flanders, Belgium. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 166, ArtID: 110220. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2020.110220>
- Doti, J. L. (2021). Examining the impact of socioeconomic variables on COVID-19 death rates at the state level. *Journal of Bioeconomics*, 23, 15–53. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s1007/s10818-021-09309-9>
- Ebert, T., Gebauer, J. E., Brenner, T., Bleidorn, W., Gosling, S. D., Potter, J., & Rentfrow, P. J. (2022). Are regional differences in psychological characteristics and their correlates robust? Applying spatial-analysis techniques to examine regional variation in personality. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 17(2), 407–441. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691621998326>
- Ebert, T., Gotz, F. M., Gladstone, J. J., Muller, S. R., & Matz, S. C. (2021). Spending reflects not only who we are but also who we are around: The joint effects of individual and geographic personality on consumption. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 121(2), 378–393.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/pspp0000344>
- Ebstrup, J. F., Eplov, L. F., Pisinger, C., & Jorgensen, T. (2011). Association between the Five Factor personality traits and perceived stress: Is the effect mediated by general self-efficacy? *Anxiety, Stress, and Coping: An International Journal*, 24(4), 407–419.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10615806.2010.540012>
- Elleman, L. G., Condon, D. M., Russin, S. E., & Revelle, W. (2018). The personality of U.S. states: Stability from 1999 to 2015. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 72, 64–72.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2016.06.022>
- FRED. (2022). *Per capita personal income by state, annual*. FRED Economic Data, St. Louis FED.
<https://fred.stlouisfed.org/release/tables?rid=110&eid=257197&od=2020-01-01>

- Friedman, H. S., Hawley, P. H., & Tucker, J. S. (1994). Personality, health, and longevity. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 3(2), 37–41. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8721.ep10769924>
- Gawthrop, E. (2022, July 19). The color of coronavirus: COVID-19 deaths by race and ethnicity in the U.S. *APM Research Lab*. <https://www.apmresearchlab.org/covid/deaths-by-race>
- Gilbert, D. G., Stunkard, M. E., Jensen, R. A., Detwiler, F. R. J., & Martinko, J. M. (1996). Effects of exam stress on mood, cortisol, and immune functioning: Influences of neuroticism and smoker—non-smoker status. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 21(2), 235–246. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0191-8869\(96\)00065-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0191-8869(96)00065-7)
- Gniewosz, G. (2023). Adolescent loneliness and negative affect during the COVID-19 pandemic: The role of extraversion and neuroticism. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 52(9), 1965–1982. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-023-01808-4>
- Golestaneh, L., Neugarten, J., Fisher, M., Billett, H. H., Gil, M. R., Johns, T., Yunes, M., Mokrzycki, M. H., Coco, M., Norris, K. C., & Perez, H. R. (2020). The association of race and COVID-19 mortality. *EClinicalMedicine*, 25, 100455. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eclinm.2020.100455>
- Gotz, F. M., Gvirtz, A., Galinsky, A. D., & Jachimowicz, J. M. (2021). How personality and policy predict pandemic behavior: Understanding sheltering-in-place in 55 countries at the onset of COVID-19. *American Psychologist*, 76(1), 39–49. <https://doi.org/10.1037/amp0000740>
- Graham-Engeland, J. E., Sin, N. L., Smyth, J. M., Jones, D. R., Knight, E. L., Sliwinski, M. J., Almeida, D. M., Katz, M. J., Lipton, R. B., & Engeland, C. G. (2018). Negative and positive affect as predictors of inflammation: Timing matters. *Brain, Behavior, and Immunity*, 74, 222–230. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbi.2018.09.011>
- Hagger, M. S., Keeck, J. J., & Hamilton, K. (2020). Managing stress during the coronavirus disease 2019 pandemic and beyond: Reappraisal and mindset approaches. *Stress and Health*, 36(3), 396–401. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smi.2969>
- Hall, M. H., Smagula, S. F., Boudreau, R. M., Ayonayon, H. N., Goldman, S. E., & Harris, T. B. (2015). Association between sleep duration and mortality is mediated by markers of inflammation and health in older adults: The Health, Aging and Body Composition Study. *Sleep: Journal of Sleep and Sleep Disorders Research*, 38(2), 189–195. <https://doi.org/10.5665/sleep.4394>
- Hawkins, R. B., Charles, E. J., & Mehaffey, J. H. (2020). Socio-economic status and COVID-19-related cases and fatalities. *Public Health*, 189, 129–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.puhe.2020.09.016>
- Hisler, G. C., Krizan, Z., DeHart, T., & Wright, A. G. C. (2020). Neuroticism as the intensity, reactivity, and variability in day-to-day affect. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 87, ArtID: 103964. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2020.103964>
- Jacobson, M., Chang, T. Y., Shah, M., Pramanik, R., & Shah, S. B. (2021). Racial and ethnic disparities in SARS-COV-2 testing and COVID-19 outcomes in a Medicaid managed care cohort. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 61(5), 644–651. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2021.05.015>
- Jemmott, J. B., III., & Locke, S. E. (1984). Psychosocial factors, immunologic mediation, and human susceptibility to infectious diseases: How much do we know? *Psychological Bulletin*, 95(1), 78–108. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.95.1.78>
- John, O. P., & Srivastava, S. (1999). The Big Five Trait taxonomy: History, measurement, and theoretical perspectives. In L. A. Pervin & O. P. John (Eds.), *Handbook of personality: Theory and research* (2nd ed., pp. 102–139). Guilford.
- Johnson, A. G., Amin, A. B., Ali, A. R., Hoots, B., Cadwell, B. L., Arora, S., Avoundjian, T., Awofeso, A. O., Barnes, J., Bayoumi, N. S., Busen, K., Chang, C., Cima, M., Crockett, M., Cronquist, A., Davidson, S., Davis, E., Delgadillo, J., Dorabawila, V., ... Scobie, H. M. (2022). Morbidity and mortality associated with COVID-19 vaccinations. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report (MMWR)*, 71(4), 132–138. <https://www.cdc.gov/mmwr/volumes/71/wr/mm7104e2.htm>
- Johnson, J. (2000). Racial and gender differences in the five factors of personality within military samples. *U.S. Department of Defense, Directorate of Research*. <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/tr/pdf/ADA389566.pdf>
- Kanazawa, S. (2022). Personality and early susceptibility to COVID-19 in the United Kingdom. *Journal of Community and Applied Social Psychology*, 32(4), 786–795. <https://doi.org/10.1002/casp.257>
- Kern, M. L., & Friedman, H. S. (2011). Personality and pathways of influence on physical health. *Social & Personality Psychology Compass*, 5(1), 76–87. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-9004.2010.00331.x>

- KFF. (2021a). *Cumulative COVID-19 cases and deaths*. Kaiser Family Foundation. <https://www.kff.org/other/state-indicator/cumulative-COVID-19-cases-and-deaths>
- KFF. (2021b). *State COVID-19 data and policy actions*. Kaiser Family Foundation. <https://www.kff.org/report-section/state-COVID-19-data-and-policy-actions-policy-actions>
- KFF. (2021c). *COVID-19 vaccines delivered and administered*. Kaiser Family Foundation. <https://www.kff.org/other/state-indicator/covid-19-vaccines-delivered-and-administered>
- KFF. (2022). *Distribution of total population by federal poverty level*. Kaiser Family Foundation. <https://www.kff.org/other/state-indicator/distribution-by-fpl>
- KFF. (2023). *Population distribution by race/ethnicity*. Kaiser Family Foundation. <https://www.kff.org/other/state-indicator/distribution-by-raceethnicity>
- Kim, J., Jasper, A., Baek, Y., & Martin, P. (2023). Personality segmentation for optimal health care: A review and proposed segmentation approach. *Psychological Studies*, 68(4), 481–488. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12646-023-00749-z>
- Kocjan, G. Z., Kavcic, T., & Avsec, A. (2021). Resilience matters: Explaining the association between personality and psychological functioning during the COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Clinical and Health Psychology*, 21(1), ArtID: 100198. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijchp.2020.08.002>
- Krizan, Z., & Hisler, G. (2019). Personality and sleep: Neuroticism and conscientiousness predict behaviourally recorded sleep years later. *European Journal of Personality*, 33(2), 133–153. <https://doi.org/10.1002/per.2191>
- Kroencke, L., Geukes, K., Utesch, T., Kuper, N., & Back, M. D. (2020). Neuroticism and emotional risk during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 89, ArtID: 104038. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2020.104038>
- Kunz, J., & Popper, C. (2020, November 5). Hospital quality and deaths from COVID-19 in U.S. counties. *Centre for Economic Policy Research (CEPR)*. <https://cepr.org/voxeu/columns/hospital-quality-and-deaths-covid-19-us-counties>
- Lamontagne, S. J., Pizzagalli, D. A., & Olmstead, M. C. (2021). Does inflammation link stress to poor COVID-19 outcome? *Stress and Health*, 37(3), 401–414. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smi.3017>
- Lazarus, R. S., & Folkman, S. (1984). *Stress, appraisal, and coping*. Springer.
- Leger, K. A., Charles, S. T., Turiano, N. A., & Almeida, D. M. (2016). Personality and stressor-related affect. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 111(6), 917–928. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pspp0000083>
- Leip, D. (2024). *Dave Leip's atlas of U.S. presidential elections*. <https://uselectionatlas.org>
- Luo, J., Zhang, B., Antonoplis, S., & Mroczek, D. K. (2024). The effects of socioeconomic status on personality development in adulthood and aging. *Journal of Personality*, 92, 243–260. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jopy.12801>
- Luo, J., Zhang, E. K., Graham, E. K., & Mroczek, D. M. (2023). Does personality always matter for health? Examining the moderating effect of age on the personality-health link from life span developmental and aging perspectives. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 125(5), 1189–1206. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pspp0000485>
- Mackey, K., Ayers, C. K., Kondo, K. K., Saha, S., Advani, S. M., Young, S., Spencer, H., Rusek, M., Anderson, J., Veazie, S., ... Smith, M. (2021). Racial and ethnic disparities in COVID-19-related infections, hospitalizations, and deaths: A systematic review. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 174(3), 362–373. <https://doi.org/10.7326/M20-6306>
- Magesh, S., John, D., Li, W. T., Li, Y., Mattingly-App, A., Jain, S., Chang, E. Y., & Ongkeko, W. M. (2021). Disparities in COVID-19 outcomes by race, ethnicity, and socioeconomic status: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *JAMA Network Open*, 4(11), e2134147. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2021.34147>
- Marsland, A. L., Bachen, E. A., & Cohen, S. (2012). Stress, immunity, and susceptibility to upper respiratory infectious disease. In A. Baum, T. A. Revenson, & J. Singer (Eds.), *Handbook of health psychology* (2nd ed., pp. 717–738). Psychology Press.
- Mathieu, E., Ritchie, H., Rodés-Guirao, L., Appel, C., Gavrillov, D., Giattino, C., Hasell, J., Macdonald, B., Dattani, S., Beltekian, D., Ortiz-Ospina, E., & Roser, M. (2020). Mortality risk of COVID-19. *Our World in Data*. <https://ourworldindata.org/mortality-risk-covid>

- McCann, S. J. H. (2008). Societal threat, authoritarianism, conservatism, and U.S. state death penalty sentencing (1977–2004). *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 94(5), 913–923. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.94.5.913>
- McCann, S. J. H. (2010). Subjective well-being, personality, demographic variables, and American state differences in smoking prevalence. *Nicotine & Tobacco Research*, 12(9), 895–904. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ntr/ntq113>
- McCann, S. J. H. (2022). Selective migration in American interstate residential flow: Similarity of Big Five personality factors among origin and destination state residents. *Current Research in Ecological and Social Psychology*, 3, 100053. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cresp.2022.100053>
- McCann, S. J. H. (2023a). Neuroticism, urbanization, and the state prevalence of Parkinson's disease in the USA. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 102(4), 10439. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2022.104319>
- McCann, S. J. H. (2023b). Relations of racial-ethnic diversity and trust to volunteering rates in the 50 American states. *Psychreg Journal of Psychology*, 7(3), 98–120. <https://doi.org/k7wc>
- McCann, S. J. H. (2024). Does diversity foster individualism? The relation of racial-ethnic diversity to individualism–collectivism across the 50 American States. *Journal of Social Psychology*, 164(3), 387–394. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224545.2022.2085073>
- McClendon, J., Chang, K., Boudreaux, J. M., Oltmanns, T. F., & Bogdan, R. (2021). Black-white racial health disparities in inflammation and physical health: Cumulative stress, social isolation, and health behaviours. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*, 131, ArtID: 105251. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psyneuen.2021.105251>
- Neelon, B., Mutiso, F., Mueller, N. T., Pearce, J. L., & Benjamin-Neelon, S. E. (2021). Spatial and temporal trends in social vulnerability and COVID-19 incidence and death rates in the United States. *PLoS One*, 16(3), e0248702. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0248702>
- Obschonka, M., Schmitt-Rodermund, E., Silbereisen, R. K., Gosling, S., & Potter, J. (2013). The regional distribution and correlates of an entrepreneurship-prone personality profile in the United States, Germany, and the United Kingdom: A socioecological perspective. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 105(1), 104–122. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0032275>
- Olsacher, A., Bade, C., Ehlers, J., & Fehring, L. (2023). How to effectively communicate health information on social media depending on the audience's personality traits: An experimental study in the context of organ donation in Germany. *Social Science & Medicine*, 335, ArtID: 116226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2023.116226>
- Pedersen, A. F., Bovbjerg, D. H., & Zachariae, R. (2011). Stress and susceptibility to infectious disease. In R. J. Contrada & A. Baum (Eds.), *The handbook of stress science: Biology, psychology, and health* (pp. 425–445). Springer.
- Pesta, B. J., Bertsch, S., McDaniel, M. A., Mahoney, C. B., & Poznanski, P. J. (2012). Differential epidemiology: IQ, neuroticism, and chronic disease by the 50 U.S. states. *Intelligence*, 40, 107–114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intell.2012.01.011>
- Peters, H., Götz, F. M., Ebert, T., Müller, S. R., Rentfrow, P. J., Gosling, S. D., Obschonka, M., Ames, D., Potter, J., & Matz, S. C. (2023). Regional personality differences predict variation in early COVID-19 infections and mobility patterns indicative of social distancing. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 124(4), 848–872. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pspp0000439>
- Pettigrew, T. F. (1997). Personality and social structure: Social psychological contributions. In R. Hogan, J. A. Johnson, & S. R. Briggs (Eds.), *Handbook of personality psychology* (pp. 417–438). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-012134645-4/50018-4>
- Poulson, M., Geary, A., Annesi, C., Allee, L., Kenzik, K., Sanchez, S., Tseng, J., & Dechert, T. (2021). National disparities in COVID-19 outcomes between Black and White Americans. *Journal of the National Medical Association*, 113(2), 125–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnma.2020.07.009>
- R. (2022). *The R project for statistical computing*. <https://www.r-project.org/>
- Regorz, A. (2020). How to interpret a collinearity diagnostics table in SPSS. *Regorz Statistics*. http://www.regorz-statistik.de/en/collinearity_diagnostics_table_SPSS.html
- Rentfrow, P. J. (2010). Statewide differences in personality: Toward a psychological geography of the United States. *American Psychologist*, 65(6), 548–558. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0018194>
- Rentfrow, P. J. (Ed.). (2014). *Geographical psychology: Exploring the interaction of environment and behavior*. American Psychological Association. <https://doi.org/10.1037/14272-000>

- Rentfrow, P. J., & Gosling, S. D. (2021). Putting personality in its place: A geographical perspective on personality traits. In O. P. John & R. W. Robins (Eds.), *Handbook of personality: Theory and research* (pp. 824–836). Guilford.
- Rentfrow, P. J., Gosling, S. D., & Potter, J. (2008). A theory of the emergence, persistence, and expression of geographic variation in psychological characteristics. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 3, 339–386. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-6924.2008.00084.x>
- Rentfrow, P. J., & Jokela, M. (2016). Geographical psychology: The spatial organization of psychological phenomena. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 25, 393–398. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721416658446>
- Rentfrow, P. J., & Jokela, M. (2019). Geographical variation in the Big Five personality domains. In D. Cohen & S. Kitayama (Eds.), *Handbook of cultural psychology* (2nd ed., pp. 768–792). Guilford.
- Rentfrow, P. J., Jokela, M., & Lamb, M. E. (2015). Regional personality differences in Great Britain. *PLoS One*, 10(3), e0122245. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0122245>
- Roberts, B. W., Kuncel, N. R., Shiner, R., Caspi, A., & Goldberg, L. R. (2007). The power of personality: The comparative validity of personality traits, socioeconomic status, and cognitive ability for predicting important life outcomes. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 2(4), 313–345. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-6916.2007.00047.x>
- Robinson, W. S. (1950). Ecological correlations and the behavior of individuals. *American Sociological Review*, 15(3), 351–357. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2087176>
- Schmidt, F. M., Sander, C., Minkwitz, J., Mergl, R., Dalton, B., Holdt, L. M., Teupser, D., Hegerl, U., & Himmerich, H. (2018). Serum markers of inflammation mediate the positive association between neuroticism and depression. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 9, 609. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2018.00609>
- Schmiedeberg, C., & Thonnissen, C. (2021). Positive and negative perceptions of the COVID-19 pandemic: Does personality play a role? *Social Science & Medicine*, 276, ArtID: 113859. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2021.113859>
- Segerstrom, S. C. (2000). Personality and the immune system: Models, methods, and mechanisms. *Annals of Behavioural Medicine*, 22(3), 180–190. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02895112>
- Shannon, J., Abraham, A., Bagwell Adams, G., & Hauer, M. (2022). Racial disparities for COVID-19 mortality in Georgia: Spatial analysis by age based on excess deaths. *Social Science & Medicine*, 292, ArtID: 114549. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2021.114549>
- Shipley, B. A., Weiss, A., Der, G., Taylor, M. D., & Deary, I. J. (2007). Neuroticism, extraversion, and mortality in the UK Health and Lifestyle Survey: A 21-year prospective cohort study. *Psychosomatic Medicine*, 69(9), 923–931. <https://doi.org/10.1097/PSY.0b013e31815abf83>
- Simonton, D. K. (2006). Presidential IQ: Presidential IQ, openness, intellectual brilliance, and leadership: Estimates and correlations for 42 U.S. chief executives. *Political Psychology*, 27, 511–526. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9221.2006.00524.x>
- Singh, P. (2023). Emotion regulation difficulties, perceived parenting and personality as predictors of health-risk behaviours among adolescents. *Current Psychology*, 42, 12896–12911. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-021-02536-3>
- Sood, L., & Sood, V. (2021). Being African American and rural: A double jeopardy from COVID-19. *Journal of Rural Health*, 37(1), 217–221. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jrh.12459>
- Statista. (2023, February 27). Death rates from COVID-19 in the United States as of February 27, 2023, by state. *Statista*. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1109011/coronavirus-covid19-death-rates-us-by-state/>
- Stephan, Y., Sutin, A. R., Luchetti, M., Aschwanden, D., & Terracciano, A. (2023). Personality and aging-related immune phenotype. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*, 153, ArtID: 106113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psyneuen.2023.106113>
- Strickhouser, J. E., Zell, E., & Krizan, Z. (2017). Does personality predict health and well-being? A metasynthesis. *Health Psychology*, 36(8), 797–810. <https://doi.org/10.1037/hea0000475>
- Suls, J., & Martin, R. (2005). The daily life of the garden-variety neurotic: Reactivity, stressor exposure, mood spillover, and maladaptive coping. *Journal of Personality*, 73(6), 1485–1510. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6494.2005.00356.x>
- Sutin, A. R., Terracciano, A., Deiana, B., Naitza, S., Ferrucci, L., Uda, M., Schlessinger, D., & Costa, P. T. (2010). High neuroticism and low conscientiousness are associated with interleukin-6. *Psychological Medicine*, 40(9), 1485–1493. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033291709992029>

- Tchicaya, A., Lorentz, N., Leduc, K., & de Lanchy, G. (2021). COVID-19 mortality with regard to healthcare services availability, health risks, and socio-spatial factors at department level in France: A spatial cross-sectional analysis. *PLoS One*, 16(9), e0256857. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0256857>
- Terracciano, A., Lockenhoff, C. E., Zonderman, A. B., Ferrucci, L., & Costa, P. T., Jr. (2008). Personality predictors of longevity: Activity, emotional stability, and conscientiousness. *Psychosomatic Medicine*, 70(6), 621–627. <https://doi.org/10.1097/PSY.0b013e31817b9371>
- Turiano, N. A., Chapman, B. P., Gruenewald, T. L., & Mroczek, D. K. (2013). Personality and the leading behavioral contributors of mortality. *Health Psychology*, 34(1), 51–60. <https://doi.org/10.1037/hea0000038>
- Turk, E., Çelik, T., Smrdu, M., Šet, J., Kuder, A., Gregorič, M., & Kralj-Fišer, S. (2023). Adherence to COVID-19 mitigation measures: The role of sociodemographic and personality factors. *Current Psychology*, 42(9), 7771–7787. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-021-02051-5>
- U.S. Census Bureau. (2022). *Educational attainment*. [https://data.census.gov/table?g=010XX00US\\$0400000&tid=ACSS1Y2018.S1501](https://data.census.gov/table?g=010XX00US$0400000&tid=ACSS1Y2018.S1501)
- U.S. Census Bureau. (2023). *Urban and rural*. <https://www.census.gov/programs-surveys/geography/guidance/geo-areas/urban-rural.html>
- Wang, X., Fang, X., Cai, Z., Wu, X., Gao, X., Min, J., & Wang, F. (2020). Comorbid chronic diseases and acute organ injuries are strongly correlated with disease severity and mortality among COVID-19 patients: A systemic review and meta-analysis. *Research*, 2020, Article ID 2402961. <https://doi.org/10.34133/2020/2402961>
- Wang, D., Gee, G. C., Bahiru, E., Yang, E. H., & Hsu, J. J. (2020). Asian-Americans and Pacific Islanders in COVID-19: Emerging disparities amid discrimination. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 35, 3685–3688. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11606-020-06264-5>
- Weston, S. J., Graham, E. K., Turiano, N. A., Aschwanden, D., Booth, T., Harrison, F., James, B. D., Lewis, N. A., Makkar, S. R., Mueller, S., & Wisniewski, K. M. (2020). Is healthy neuroticism associated with chronic conditions? A coordinated integrative data analysis. *Collabra: Psychology*, 6(1), 42. <https://doi.org/10.1525/collabra.267>
- Williamson, E. J., Walker, A. J., Bhaskaran, K., Bacon, S., Bates, C., Morton, C. E., Curtis, H. J., Mehrkar, A., Evans, D., Inglesby, P., & Cockburn, J. (2020). Factors associated with COVID-19-related death using OpenSAFELY. *Nature*, 584(7821), 430–436. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2521-4>
- Wilson, R. S., Mendes de Leon, C. F., Bienias, J. L., Evans, D. A., & Bennet, D. A. (2004). Personality and mortality in old age. *Journals of Gerontology: Series B*, 59(3), P110–P116. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geronb/59.3.P110>
- Wrzus, C., Luong, G., Wagner, G. G., & Riediger, M. (2021). Longitudinal coupling of momentary stress reactivity and trait neuroticism: Specificity of states, traits, and age period. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 121(3), 691–706. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pspp0000308>
- Xia, Y., Xia, C., Wu, L., Zheng, L., Hui, L., & Zhang, J. (2023). Systemic Immune Inflammation Index (SII), System Inflammation Response Index (SIRI) and risk of all-cause mortality and cardiovascular mortality: A 20-year follow-up cohort study of 42,875 US adults. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 12(3), 1128. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm12031128>
- Yan, B. W., Hwang, A. L., Ng, F., Chu, J. N., Tsoh, J. Y., & Nguyen, T. T. (2021). Death toll of COVID-19 on Asian Americans: Disparities revealed. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 36, 3545–3549. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11606-021-07003-0>
- Yee, A. (2021, May 6). COVID's outsize impact on Asian Americans is being ignored. *Scientific American*. <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/covids-outsize-impact-on-asian-americans-is-being-ignored/>
- Zhang, F., Cao, H., & Baranova, A. (2022). Genetic variation mediating neuroticism's influence on cardiovascular diseases. *Journal of Psychopathology and Clinical Science*, 131(3), 278–286. <https://doi.org/10.1037/abn0000744>
- Zidkova, R., Malinakova, K., van Dijk, J. P., & Tavel, P. (2023). COVID-19 vaccination refusal—Which factors are related in the Czech Republic, one of the most affected countries in the world? *International Journal of Public Health*, 68, ArtID: 1605375. <https://doi.org/10.3389/ijph.2023.1605375>